

National Security and Deposit Money Banks Compliance with Banking Ethics

Sharlywest Uwabor EBOIGBE PhD.

Department of Finance, University of Benin, Benin City
sharlywest.eboigbe@uniben.edu
+23408056611838

Theophilus Eghosa AKADI

Banking and Finance, Auchu polytechnic, Auchu
akadi4u@gmail.com
+234 813 838 7227

Ozimehede Muhammad MUSTAFA

University of Benin, Benin City.
ozimehede@gmail.com
+234 803 829 3780

Abstract

This study examined the effect of national security factors such as cybersecurity, physical security, economic security, and legal/regulatory security on banking ethics in Nigeria's Deposit Money Banks (DMBs). Against the backdrop of increasing concerns about the nexus between security and financial system integrity, the study explored how these security dimensions shape ethical conduct among banking personnel and regulators. Using a convenience sampling technique and Cochran's formula for unknown populations, a minimum sample size of 384 respondents was determined. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using a Generalized Linear Model (GLM), following diagnostic tests which revealed the presence of serial correlation. The findings indicate that cybersecurity has a positive and statistically significant effect on banking ethics, highlighting the importance of digital resilience in promoting ethical practices. Conversely, physical security shows a significant negative effect, while economic security exhibits a negative but marginally significant relationship with banking ethics. Legal and regulatory security, although positive, does not have a statistically significant impact. These results suggest that ethical behaviour in Nigerian banks is driven more by effective cybersecurity systems, while traditional security and regulatory mechanisms may not yield the desired ethical outcomes without strong institutional enforcement and internal ethical commitment. The study recommends that banks prioritize investments in cybersecurity infrastructure and digital risk management systems, while also strengthening internal ethical culture, governance practices, and regulatory effectiveness. An integrated approach that combines technological security with institutional accountability is essential for enhancing banking ethics and supporting national security objectives.

Keywords: Cybersecurity; Financial Institutions; National security; Economic security; Government Policy and Regulation

JEL Classification: L5, G21, F52, F50, G28

Open Access This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons licence, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons licence, unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons licence and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. To view a copy of this licence, visit <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.

1. Introduction

The ethical foundations of the banking sector play a pivotal role in determining financial system stability, public trust, and sustainable economic development (Kiruthika et al., 2024). In Nigeria, banking ethics encompass values such as integrity, transparency, fiduciary responsibility, and regulatory compliance (Gasu, 2023). These ethical standards are codified in professional codes of conduct and reinforced by supervisory institutions like the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and the Nigerian Deposit Insurance Corporation (NDIC). However, studies have consistently highlighted ethical lapses ranging from insider abuse, concealment of non-performing loans, to outright financial fraud in Nigerian banks (Okodugha, 2021; Egejuru, 2023). The systemic nature of these issues undermines investor confidence, reduces foreign direct investment, and weakens the overall credibility of the sector (Osuma et al., 2024). With the increasing digitization of banking services and the proliferation of technology-driven platforms, ethical responsibilities are no longer confined to traditional banking processes but now extend to the protection of customer data, prevention of cyber breaches, and responsible automation (Arcot et al., 2024). Thus, banking ethics in Nigeria today must be viewed not only through a moral or compliance lens but also within broader institutional and security-based frameworks.

The concept of national security has evolved significantly, expanding beyond its classical focus on territorial integrity and military readiness to incorporate economic, technological, and cyber dimensions (Fischerkeller et al., 2022; Slawotsky, 2024). Within this broader framework, financial institutions are now seen as critical national assets whose stability and operational integrity directly relate to national security imperatives (Fischerkeller et al., 2022). In Nigeria, the banking sector is particularly vulnerable to multiple security threats, including cyberattacks, physical terrorism (e.g., attacks on bank branches in conflict-prone regions), economic sabotage, and regulatory sabotage through money laundering or terrorism financing (Ugbe, 2021). The interdependence between financial security and national stability has been further intensified by the growing integration of the Nigerian banking sector into global financial networks, exposing it to transnational security threats (Ayemere, 2025). Consequently, national security concerns whether in the form of cybersecurity resilience, physical infrastructure protection, or anti-corruption enforcement can directly affect ethical behaviour within banks, particularly in areas like risk reporting, whistleblowing, anti-money laundering (AML) compliance, and corporate transparency (Fatoki, 2023).

Against this backdrop, there is a compelling rationale to investigate how national security influences banking ethics in Nigeria. While previous research has examined banking ethics from perspectives such as organizational culture (Abunike & Onyinye, 2025), governance failures (Torku & Laryea, 2021), or regulatory enforcement (Ononiwu et al., 2024), there remains a critical gap in linking ethical conduct to dimensions of national security. As security threats become more multidimensional ranging from digital espionage to insider collusion in fraudulent schemes understanding their influence on ethical compliance becomes essential for policy formulation and institutional reform. Moreover, in a country like Nigeria, where systemic corruption and security fragility intersect with weak institutional capacity (Okoye et

al., 2025), evaluating how threats to national security affect the ethical conduct of banks offers a unique lens for strengthening both financial governance and national resilience.

Despite growing interest in the ethical dimensions of financial services, empirical studies addressing the intersection between security dynamics and ethical banking behaviour remain limited in both scope and contextual relevance. For instance, Ruth et al. (2022) offer valuable insights into how ethical climate shapes employees' cybersecurity-related ethical behaviour in Ugandan banks, but their findings are confined to the behavioural intentions of staff and do not extend to institutional or systemic ethical practices. Moreover, their analysis reveals that ethical climate does not moderate the influence of cardinal virtues such as prudence and justice on cybersecurity behaviour, though it does have a direct effect. This points to an underexplored area: how broader external security threats such as national-level cyber risks or regulatory instability impact not just individual behaviours but institutional ethical frameworks. Similarly, the study by Khalil et al. (2021) investigates the financial costs of cybersecurity within e-banking in Pakistan and finds that cybersecurity investments significantly affect both innovation and financial performance. However, the ethical implications of these cybersecurity strategies particularly how they influence or constrain ethical banking conduct are not explicitly examined. These studies tend to isolate internal factors (like ethical climate or innovation outcomes), while overlooking how external security threats (cyber, economic, or regulatory) systematically affect ethical decision-making at the organizational level, particularly in fragile or high-risk environments.

Furthermore, while Alhammedi et al. (2022) explore ethical banking performance from the perspective of Maqāsid al-Sharī'ah, their research is confined to Islamic banks and relies heavily on doctrinal benchmarks rather than on the broader, real-time security and regulatory challenges facing financial institutions. Although their findings reveal that ethical performance often comes at a financial cost, the study is grounded in a religious and philosophical framework that may not translate directly to secular banking systems or jurisdictions such as Nigeria. What remains critically under-investigated is how national security risks ranging from cyber and physical threats to economic sabotage and regulatory laxity shape the ethical posture of banking institutions in real-world operational contexts. Current empirical literature provides limited cross-sectoral analysis that connects national security variables to ethical banking outcomes. Consequently, there is a notable absence of research exploring how different dimensions of national security cybersecurity, physical insecurity, economic instability, and legal-regulatory uncertainty collectively influence banking ethics in emerging economies. It is within this intersectoral nexus that the current study seeks to anchor its inquiry, raising critical questions about how national security challenges shape the ethical contours of Nigerian banking practices and how institutions navigate the tension between security compliance, ethical responsibility, and financial performance.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Formulation

2.1. Banking ethics

Banking ethics refers to the application of moral principles and standards to the operations, practices, and decision-making processes within banking institutions, encompassing fairness,

transparency, integrity, accountability, and responsibility in dealing with stakeholders (Rovera, 2022). At its core, banking ethics aims to ensure that financial institutions do not merely pursue profit maximization but also uphold societal trust and long-term sustainability in the financial system (Valls Martínez et al., 2021). Ethical banking behaviour extends to areas such as lending practices, customer confidentiality, anti-money laundering compliance, corporate governance, and truthful financial reporting (Gonsolin, 2023). However, in practice, the ethical conduct of banks is often challenged by inherent conflicts of interest, profit-driven cultures, regulatory arbitrage, and systemic opacity, which have historically contributed to financial scandals and institutional failures (Omarova, 2017). Critics argue that despite the proliferation of ethics codes and corporate social responsibility (CSR) frameworks, many banks continue to engage in ethically questionable practices such as predatory lending, excessive risk-taking, and data manipulation, highlighting a gap between ethical rhetoric and real institutional behaviour (Vevere & Svirina, 2020). Furthermore, the increasing automation of banking through FinTech raises new ethical dilemmas related to algorithmic bias, data privacy, and digital exclusion (Aldboush & Ferdous, 2023). While ethical banking is often framed as a compliance issue, a more critical view sees it as a governance challenge, requiring cultural transformation, stakeholder engagement, and stronger regulatory frameworks to embed ethical considerations into core banking strategies (Viganò, 2020). Thus, banking ethics should be seen not merely as an idealised value set but as a pragmatic framework for balancing profitability with public accountability in an evolving financial landscape.

2.2. National security

National security refers to the safeguarding of a nation's sovereignty, territorial integrity, political stability, and socio-economic wellbeing from internal and external threats, encompassing both traditional and non-traditional dimensions of state protection (Kitler, 2021). Traditionally, national security was primarily framed through the lens of military defence and state-centric geopolitics, prioritizing armed conflict, espionage, and border control (Clarke et al., 2022). However, contemporary scholarship has significantly expanded the scope to include issues such as cyber threats, economic stability, terrorism, environmental risks, health pandemics, and even financial system integrity, reflecting the multidimensional and evolving nature of modern security challenges (Heath, 2019). Critics argue that the concept is often deployed ambiguously, sometimes manipulated to justify authoritarian policies, restrict civil liberties, or marginalize dissent under the guise of national interest (Hill, 2020). Additionally, the securitization of previously non-security domains such as migration, technology, and even banking has raised ethical and democratic concerns about the balance between state power and individual freedoms (Broecker, 2022). In the digital era, national security increasingly involves the protection of critical information infrastructure, financial institutions, and national data assets from cyber-attacks and systemic vulnerabilities (Basak, 2024). Moreover, the interdependence of global systems means that a breach in one nation's security architecture be it digital, economic, or environmental can have transnational ripple effects, challenging traditional notions of sovereignty and unilateral defence (Bu, 2024). Therefore, national security must be understood not merely as a defensive posture but as a complex, contested, and politically charged framework that requires critical reflection on whose interests are served, who defines the threats, and how inclusive and accountable the protective mechanisms are.

2.3. Cybersecurity

Cybersecurity refers to the strategic practices, technologies, and institutional frameworks designed to protect digital infrastructure, networks, and data from unauthorized access, damage, or disruption (AlDaajeh & Alrabaaee, 2024). As digital systems become integral to national governance, finance, and public services, cybersecurity has emerged as a critical national security concern, encompassing not only state-level cyber defence but also the resilience of private-sector infrastructure (Adeyeri & Abroshan, 2024). The concept goes beyond technical protection to include risk management, cyber deterrence, and public trust in digital governance (Naseir, 2021). However, critics argue that cybersecurity discourse is often dominated by military-industrial narratives, leading to the securitization of cyberspace in ways that justify surveillance, censorship, and the erosion of digital rights (McRae et al., 2022; Cavely, 2024). Moreover, the asymmetry of cyber warfare where non-state actors can inflict disproportionate harm exposes the inadequacy of conventional security doctrines in the digital age (Pijpers & Arnold, 2025). As such, cybersecurity must be understood not only as a technical imperative but as a socio-political construct that shapes power dynamics, governance legitimacy, and the ethics of state control in an increasingly digitized society.

2.4. Physical security

Physical security refers to the protection of individuals, infrastructure, and state assets from physical threats such as terrorism, armed conflict, insurgency, sabotage, and natural disasters (Martellini & Abaimov, 2022). It remains the most traditional pillar of national security, historically focused on military readiness, policing, and border control mechanisms. Despite its foundational role, physical security has been critiqued for its often narrow, state-centric framing that prioritizes regime stability over human security or civil liberties (Rossi & Riemann, 2024). In post-9/11 security governance, the expansion of physical surveillance and militarization of public spaces has sparked debates about the trade-off between safety and freedom (Bradley et al., 2023). Moreover, the increasing reliance on technology such as biometrics, drones, and AI-enabled surveillance for physical security raises ethical concerns around privacy, accountability, and misuse of force (Sindiramutty et al., 2024). Thus, while physical security is essential for national resilience, it must be critically evaluated for its broader socio-political impacts, including the risks of authoritarian overreach and systemic discrimination.

2.5. Economic security

Economic security refers to the capacity of a state to protect and sustain the financial wellbeing of its citizens and institutions through stable access to resources, employment, production, and trade (Elagin et al., 2021). It includes safeguarding national assets, critical industries, financial markets, and supply chains from internal vulnerabilities and external shocks, such as global financial crises, sanctions, or economic espionage (Sheikh et al., 2022). Economic security is often linked to broader developmental goals, including poverty alleviation, inequality reduction, and macroeconomic stability. However, its definition is contested, with critics warning that nationalistic interpretations can justify protectionism, exploitative trade policies, and corporate bailouts that privilege elites over broader public interests (Gelter, 2022). Furthermore, the globalization of finance has made national economies increasingly

susceptible to transnational risks such as currency manipulation or systemic banking failures that exceed domestic regulatory control (Arkhipov et al., 2021). As such, economic security must be approached not just as a state-driven agenda for growth, but as a multidimensional construct requiring equity, transparency, and international cooperation.

2.6. Legal/regulatory security

Legal or regulatory security encompasses the frameworks, institutions, and rule-of-law mechanisms that ensure predictability, accountability, and fairness in the protection of national interests and citizen rights (Paleri, 2022). It involves constitutional law, financial regulation, data protection, anti-terrorism legislation, and institutional oversight, serving as both a deterrent against lawlessness and a safeguard against the abuse of power. In the context of national security, legal structures are expected to balance the imperative of state protection with the preservation of civil liberties and democratic accountability (Ojo & Ayo, 2023). However, legal security can become compromised when emergency powers, opaque regulatory regimes, or weak judicial independence enable the erosion of rights under the pretext of national safety (Akanle & Akanle, 2022). Moreover, the rapid emergence of technologies like AI and FinTech often outpaces existing legal frameworks, leading to regulatory gaps that expose societies to financial crimes, surveillance, and algorithmic bias (Kandpal et al., 2025). Therefore, legal/regulatory security must be understood as a dynamic field with constant revision, ethical scrutiny, and participatory governance to uphold the legitimacy of national security objectives.

2.7. Empirical review

Ruth et al. (2022) examined the role of ethical climate in moderating the relationship between cardinal virtues (prudence, temperance, courage, and justice) and cybersecurity ethical behaviour intentions among employees in Ugandan commercial banks. Drawing on ethical climate theory and using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) on data from 240 bank employees, the study found that while the ethical climate significantly influenced cybersecurity ethical behaviour, it did not moderate the effect of the cardinal virtues. The results imply that a strong ethical climate can enhance ethical cybersecurity conduct independently, but it does not significantly alter how virtues translate into ethical behaviour.

Alhammadi et al. (2022) evaluated the ethical performance of Islamic banks in Indonesia through the lens of Maqāṣid al-Sharī‘ah, focusing on justice, education, and wealth distribution. Using a content analysis of annual reports and the Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) method, the study revealed a performance gap: conventional financial indicators failed to capture Islamic banks’ broader ethical objectives. Although some banks demonstrated strong alignment with Maqāṣid al-Sharī‘ah values, achieving high ethical scores was often accompanied by financial trade-offs, indicating a tension between ethical commitment and profitability in Islamic banking. Khalil et al. (2021) explored the impact of various cybersecurity cost components (prevention, detection, response, and development costs) on product innovation performance (PIP) and financial performance (FP) in Pakistan’s e-banking sector. Employing multivariate statistical methods on survey data from managerial-level e-banking staff, the study found that most cybersecurity costs (excluding indirect costs) positively influenced both innovation and financial outcomes. Furthermore, PIP partially

mediated the relationship between direct cybersecurity costs and financial performance, suggesting that investment in cybersecurity enhances not only security posture but also innovation-driven profitability.

Moshi (2024) examined the effect of perceived security risks on mobile banking adoption among fashion retailers in Tanzania using Perceived Risk Theory. Data from 200 respondents were analysed with binary logistic regression. The study found that fraud, phishing, and transaction errors negatively influence adoption, while security literacy enhances it. The study emphasizes the need for improved cybersecurity awareness and stronger authentication systems. Similarly, Mgiba and Mxotwa (2024) investigated how cybersecurity communication shapes ethical concerns, satisfaction, and loyalty in AI-enabled banking using Structural Equation Modelling. The findings show that effective communication significantly influences privacy and security concerns, which in turn enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty, although diversity and discrimination concerns were not significant.

Khaleel et al. (2022) assessed ethical practices in Islamic banks in Pakistan using content analysis and survey methods. The results indicate generally satisfactory ethical standards, though variations exist across banks, with recommendations for improved reporting and employee training. Furthermore, Suandi, Herri, Yuliharsi, and Syafrizal (2023) analysed the impact of Islamic marketing ethics and convergence marketing on bank performance using PLS-SEM. The study found that both factors significantly improve competitive advantage, which in turn drives bank performance, indicating an indirect relationship.

2.8. Theoretical framework

Three major theories underpin the study of national security and banking ethics: stakeholder theory, social contract theory, and institutional theory. Stakeholder theory, advanced by Freeman (1984), argues that organizations exist not only to maximize shareholder wealth but also to serve the interests of multiple stakeholders, including employees, customers, regulators, communities, and society at large. In banking, this perspective is highly relevant because banks operate within a network of relationships affected by ethical or unethical conduct. In relation to national security, banks are expected to safeguard not only financial assets but also informational and infrastructural systems. In insecure environments characterized by cyber threats, terrorism financing, and weak regulation, banks must adopt ethical and risk-sensitive practices that protect stakeholder trust and national interest (Clarkson, 1995; Jones, 1995). However, critics note that Stakeholder Theory often lacks clarity in resolving conflicting stakeholder interests and may assume overly moral corporate behaviour (Goodpaster, 1991; Phillips, 2003).

Social contract theory, particularly the integrative version developed by Donaldson and Dunfee (1994), explains that institutions are bound by both universal ethical principles and context-specific societal expectations. In the Nigerian banking sector, threats such as insurgency financing, fraud, and regulatory evasion have intensified public expectations for honesty, transparency, and fairness. Banks therefore operate under an implicit contract with society: they enjoy legitimacy in return for ethical conduct that supports public welfare and national

security (Van Oosterhout et al., 2006). When banks facilitate suspicious transactions or fail to report unethical practices, they violate this contract and risk losing social legitimacy. A major limitation, however, is that the theory assumes shared moral norms, which may be weak in pluralistic and institutionally fragile settings like Nigeria (Painter-Morland, 2006).

Institutional theory provides a structural explanation of how ethical behaviour is shaped by formal rules, cultural norms, and environmental pressures (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983; Scott, 2001). In Nigeria, coercive pressures such as anti-money laundering laws, cybersecurity regulations, and CBN oversight are meant to enforce ethical conduct. Yet institutional weaknesses, including inconsistent enforcement and political interference, often normalize unethical practices (North, 1990; Adegbite, 2015). Mimetic adoption of global standards may also be symbolic rather than genuine, reflecting what Meyer and Rowan (1977) describe as decoupling. Thus, Institutional Theory offers a practical lens for understanding banking ethics within fragile national security contexts.

Based on the reviewed literature and the study variables, the following hypotheses are formulated:

H01: Cybersecurity has no significant effect on banking ethics among Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

H02: Physical security has no significant effect on banking ethics among Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

H03: Economic security has no significant effect on banking ethics among Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

H04: Legal and regulatory security have no significant effect on banking ethics among Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research design

This study adopts a descriptive cross-sectional survey design, which is suitable for capturing the perceptions and behavioural patterns of banking professionals at a specific point in time (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). The descriptive approach enables the systematic documentation and analysis of the relationship between national security dimensions and banking ethics, while the cross-sectional nature facilitates the efficient collection of data from a large and diverse respondent pool (Saunders et al., 2019). This design is particularly appropriate for organizational and ethical inquiries, where the phenomena of interest such as ethical conduct are not easily manipulated or experimentally controlled (Bryman, 2016).

The study targets employees from Tier 1 DMBs in Nigeria. These includes Access Bank Plc, First Bank of Nigeria Ltd, United Bank for Africa Plc, Zenith Bank Plc, and Guaranty Trust Bank Plc, due to their extensive operational scope and systemic significance (CBN, 2023) and the banks share in the industry. The population includes banking staff, compliance officers,

and regulatory officials. Using the convenience sampling technique to facilitate access to eligible respondents, especially in contexts with limited institutional cooperation a method endorsed for exploratory studies within organizational settings (Etikan et al., 2016). Since the population size is not precisely known, Cochran's formula for sample size estimation for an unknown population was employed (Cochran, 1977), yielding a minimum required sample size of 384 respondents to achieve a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error.

Primary data were collected through structured questionnaire, administered to employees across the selected Tier 1 banks. The questionnaire employed a five-point Likert scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree (1)" to "Strongly Agree (5)," which is widely recommended for attitudinal and behavioural research (Likert, 1932; Boone & Boone, 2012). The instrument was designed to capture multi-dimensional constructs related to banking ethics and national security perceptions. Given the professional nature of the respondents, the use of a self-administered questionnaire facilitated anonymity and encouraged more candid responses (Fink, 2013). Ethical clearance was obtained, and all responses were treated with strict confidentiality in line with standard research ethics protocols (Babbie, 2020).

3.2. Model specification

This study models the relationship between national security dimensions and banking ethics using a multiple linear regression framework (Gujarati & Porter, 2009; Wooldridge, 2016).

The functional form of the model is:

$$BE = f(CYS, PHS, ECS, LRS, \epsilon) \text{-----(i)}$$

The corresponding econometric model is expressed as:

$$BE_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1CYS_i + \beta_2PHS_i + \beta_3ECS_i + \beta_4LRS_i + \mu_i \text{-----(ii)}$$

Where: BE_i = Banking Ethics score for respondent I , CYS_i = Cybersecurity perception for respondent I , PHS_i = Physical security perception for respondent I , ECS_i = Economic security perception for respondent I , LRS_i = Legal and regulatory security perception for respondent I , β_0 = Constant (intercept), β_1 – β_4 = Regression coefficients and μ_i = Stochastic error term.

With A Priori Expectations of β_1 - $\beta_4 > 0$, This implies that improvements in any dimension of national security are hypothesized to lead to stronger ethical behaviour among banks.

3.3. Operationalization of variables

The variables in this study were operationalized based on conceptual frameworks in ethics, security studies, and organizational behaviour. The dependent variable, banking ethics (BE), was measured using items related to ethical codes adherence, transparency, conflict of interest management, and whistle-blowing practices (Valentine & Barnett, 2003; Treviño et al., 1998). The independent variables include cybersecurity (CYS), measured by breach frequency, firewall robustness, and employee vigilance (Whitman & Mattord, 2018); physical security (PHS), measured by physical infrastructure safeguards and risk exposure (Sutton & Stewart,

2002); economic security (ECS), captured through perceptions of financial system stability and macroeconomic threats (Baldwin, 1997); and legal/regulatory security (LRS), evaluated via perceived consistency and efficacy of legal and regulatory frameworks (La Porta et al., 1998). Table 1 is a snapshot of the measurement for the variables and their sources.

Table 1: Measurement of Variables

Variable	Construct/Dimension	Indicators	Measurement Scale	Sources
Banking Ethics (BE)	Ethical Conduct and Compliance	Adherence to ethical codes, transparency in reporting, whistleblowing policy, conflict of interest declaration	5-point Likert Scale	Valentine & Barnett (2003); Treviño et al. (1998)
Cybersecurity (CYS)	Information Security Measures	Incident response protocols, firewall strength, staff vigilance, cybersecurity training	5-point Likert Scale	Whitman & Mattord (2018)
Physical Security (PHS)	Facility Protection and Safety	Building access control, physical surveillance, disaster readiness, ATM/banking hall security	5-point Likert Scale	Sutton & Stewart (2002)
Economic Security (ECS)	Economic Stability Threats	Exchange rate instability, inflation trends, market volatility, financial system risk	5-point Likert Scale	Baldwin (1997)
Legal/Regulatory Security (LRS)	Regulatory Clarity and Enforcement	Adequacy of legal frameworks, clarity of compliance rules, regulatory enforcement, audit oversight	5-point Likert Scale	La Porta et al. (1998)

Author's Compilation (2025)

The study established face and content validity through expert reviews involving academics and practitioners in financial ethics, national security, and regulatory compliance, an approach consistent with best practices in instrument development (Haynes et al., 1995). To assess reliability, Cronbach's Alpha was computed for each construct to evaluate internal consistency. According to Nunnally and Bernstein (1994), alpha values above 0.70 are acceptable for social science research. Items with low item-total correlation were reviewed or removed to ensure overall instrument reliability (Tavakol & Dennick, 2011; Table 2).

Table 2: Reliability Scores

S/N	Variable / Scale	Items	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Cases	Remark
1	Banking Ethics (BE)	BE1–BE5	0.980	30	Highly Reliable
2	Cybersecurity (CYS)	CYS1–CYS5	0.763	30	Reliable
3	Physical Security (PHS)	PHS1–PHS5	0.753	30	Reliable
4	Economic Security (ECS)	ECS1–ECS5	0.776	30	Reliable
5	Legal and Regulatory Security (LRS)	LRS1–LRS5	0.771	30	Reliable

Author's Compilation (2025)

Data were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods. Descriptive statistics, including means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions, were used to summarize respondents' characteristics and responses. Inferentially, a multiple regression analysis was employed to estimate the effect of national security dimensions on banking ethics, a method suitable for identifying causal relationships in multivariate settings (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). ANOVA was used to determine the significance of variance across groups. Diagnostic checks for multicollinearity (Variance Inflation Factor), heteroscedasticity (Breusch-Pagan test), and model misspecification (Ramsey RESET test) were conducted to confirm the robustness of the regression results (Wooldridge, 2016).

4. Results and Discussions

This section presented the empirical analysis via descriptive and inferential analysis, alongside several diagnostic tests.

Table 3 Descriptive Statistics of Common Sample

	BE	CYS	PHS	ECS	LRS
Mean	2.792878	3.304451	3.424926	3.330564	2.877151
Std. Dev.	0.595976	0.624317	0.724467	0.634558	0.662054
Skewness	-0.048580	0.073127	-0.082341	-0.246369	0.111568
Kurtosis	2.271773	3.137226	2.440299	3.401718	2.874540
Jarque-Bera	7.579056	0.564775	4.779571	5.675193	0.920143
Probability	0.022606	0.753982	0.091649	0.058566	0.631239

Source: Author's Compilation (2025) from EViews 12

The descriptive statistics in Table 3 indicate moderate variation across Banking Ethics (BE), Cybersecurity (CYS), Physical Security (PHS), Economic Security (ECS), and Legal and Regulatory Security (LRS), with mean values ranging from 2.79 (BE) to 3.42 (PHS), suggesting generally average perceptions among respondents. The standard deviations (0.596–0.724) reflect reasonable dispersion across all constructs. Skewness values are close to zero, indicating approximate symmetry, while kurtosis values are around 3, suggesting near-normal distributions. The Jarque-Bera results show that Cybersecurity (CYS), Physical Security (PHS), Economic Security (ECS), and Legal and Regulatory Security (LRS) do not significantly deviate from normality, whereas Banking Ethics (BE) shows slight non-normality ($p < 0.05$). Overall, the data are sufficiently normally distributed and suitable for further analysis.

Table 4 Correlation Matrix and Multicollinearity Test

	BE	CYS	PHS	ECS	LRS	VIF
BE	1.000000					
CYS	0.096711	1.000000				1.390919
PHS	-0.211619*	0.474315*	1.000000			1.703782
ECS	-0.247477*	0.051417	0.377453*	1.000000		1.852070
LRS	0.240658*	0.018752*	-0.414550	-0.669285*	1.000000	2.016528

Note: * Sig @ 1%; ** Sig @ 5%

Source: Author's Compilation from Eviews Version 12

The correlation matrix in Table 4 reveals generally weak to moderate relationships among the variables. Specifically, BE shows weak positive association with CYS (0.097) and LRS (0.241), but a significant negative relationship with PHS (-0.212) and ECS (-0.247). CYS is moderately and positively related to PHS (0.474), while PHS also shows a positive relationship with ECS (0.377). However, LRS exhibits a strong negative relationship with ECS (-0.669) and a moderate negative association with PHS (-0.415). Most of these relationships are statistically significant at either the 1% or 5% level, indicating meaningful interactions among the variables. Furthermore, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values range from 1.391 to 2.017, which are well below the threshold of 10, confirming the absence of multicollinearity.

The diagnostic results in Table 5 show that the model is free from heteroskedasticity and specification error but suffers from serial correlation. Specifically, the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test is significant (Prob. F = 0.0000; Prob. Chi-Square = 0.0000), confirming the presence of serial correlation in the model residuals. However, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test is not significant (Prob. F = 0.7364; Prob. Chi-Square = 0.7331), indicating the absence of heteroskedasticity, while the Ramsey RESET test is also insignificant (Prob. F = 0.2741; Likelihood ratio = 0.2695), suggesting that the model is correctly specified. Therefore, owing to the problem of serial correlation, the Generalized Linear Model (GLM) was adopted to obtain more efficient and reliable estimates

Table 5 Diagnostics Test: Serial, Heteroskedasticity, and Specification Tests

<i>Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:</i>			
F-statistic	10.73748	Prob. F(2,330)	0.0000
Obs*R-squared	20.59054	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0000
<i>Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey</i>			
F-statistic	0.499186	Prob. F(4,332)	0.7364
Obs*R-squared	2.014700	Prob. Chi-Square(4)	0.7331
<i>Ramsey RESET Test: Specification: BE CYS PHS ECS LRS C</i>			
t-statistic	1.095413	331	0.2741
F-statistic	1.199930	(1, 331)	0.2741
Likelihood ratio	1.219472	1	0.2695

Source: Researcher's compilation (2025)

Table 6: Multivariate Analysis

Dependent Variable: BE

Generalized Linear Model (GLM)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
CYS	0.209907	0.058041	3.616557	0.0003
PHS	-0.202767	0.055357	-3.662891	0.0002
ECS	-0.129000	0.065894	-1.957698	0.0503
LRS	0.038193	0.065901	0.579547	0.5622
C	3.113469	0.405731	7.673726	0.0000

LR statistic: 44.25852

Prob(LR statistic): 0.000000

Source: Researcher's compilation (2025)

The Generalized Linear Model (GLM) results in Table 6 show that Cybersecurity (CYS) has a positive and statistically significant effect on Banking Ethics (BE) ($\beta = 0.2099$, $p = 0.0003$), implying that stronger cybersecurity frameworks significantly enhance ethical compliance in the banking sector. This supports studies which argue that digital resilience, data protection, and secure information systems are central to sustaining ethical standards and institutional trust in financial organizations (AlDaajeh & Alrabae, 2024; Sheikh et al., 2022). The result is also consistent with the view that cybersecurity is not merely a technical requirement but a core ethical responsibility of banks, since breaches in digital systems can undermine customer confidence and organizational legitimacy (Naseir, 2021; Pijpers & Arnold, 2025). In contrast, Physical Security (PHS) exerts a negative and significant effect on Banking Ethics ($\beta = -0.2028$, $p = 0.0002$), while Economic Security (ECS) also shows a negative effect that is only marginally significant at the 5% level ($\beta = -0.1290$, $p = 0.0503$). These negative signs suggest that increases in physical and economic security measures, within the present sample, do not necessarily translate into stronger ethical behaviour and may reflect reactive or compliance-driven systems rather than deeply embedded ethical values.

Furthermore, Legal and Regulatory Security (LRS) has a positive but statistically insignificant effect on Banking Ethics ($\beta = 0.0382$, $p = 0.5622$), indicating that legal and regulatory

structures alone do not significantly drive ethical conduct in the studied context. This aligns with arguments that formal rules and regulatory controls may be insufficient where enforcement is weak or where ethical behaviour is not internalized within organizational culture (Rossi & Riemann, 2024; Ojo & Ayo, 2023). It also supports concerns in the literature that regulatory frameworks can become less effective when affected by institutional weaknesses or implementation gaps (Akanle & Akanle, 2022; Kandpal et al., 2025). Overall, the model is statistically significant, as shown by the LR statistic of 44.2585 with $p = 0.0000$, suggesting that the explanatory variables jointly influence banking ethics.

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

This study examined the relationship between cybersecurity, physical security, economic security, legal and regulatory security, and banking ethics among Nigerian financial institutions. The findings show that cybersecurity has a positive and statistically significant influence on banking ethics, indicating that stronger digital protection systems enhance ethical conduct in the banking sector. In contrast, physical security has a significant negative effect on banking ethics, while economic security also exerts a negative effect that is only marginally significant. Legal and regulatory security, although positive, does not significantly influence banking ethics. These results suggest that banking ethics in Nigeria is shaped more strongly by cybersecurity practices, while physical, economic, and regulatory mechanisms may not automatically translate into ethical behaviour unless they are supported by deeper institutional commitment and internal ethical culture. This partly supports stakeholder theory and institutional theory by showing that ethical banking outcomes depend not only on formal controls but also on how such mechanisms are embedded within organizational systems and practices.

Based on these findings, Nigerian financial institutions should give greater priority to strengthening cybersecurity infrastructure, data protection systems, and digital risk management frameworks as a means of improving ethical standards and stakeholder trust. Banks should also critically review existing physical and economic security arrangements to ensure that such measures do not remain merely reactive or compliance-driven, but are aligned with ethical leadership, transparency, and accountability. In addition, regulators should go beyond formal rule enforcement by promoting effective implementation, ethical monitoring, and institutional reforms that encourage genuine compliance rather than symbolic adherence. Overall, a more integrated approach that combines strong cybersecurity, sound governance, staff training, and effective regulatory oversight is necessary to enhance banking ethics and support national security objectives in Nigeria.

References

- Abunike, U. E., & Onyinye, I. A. (2025). Exploring the relationship between organizational culture and white-collar crime in financial institutions in Anambra state. *AMAMIHE Journal of Applied Philosophy*, 23(1), DOI:10.13140/RG.2.2.26216.17920
- Adegbite, E. (2015). Good corporate governance in Nigeria: Antecedents, propositions and peculiarities. *International Business Review*, 24(2), 319–330.

- Adeyeri, A., & Abroshan, H. (2024). Geopolitical ramifications of cybersecurity threats: state responses and international cooperations in the digital warfare era. *Information*, 15(11), 682, <https://doi.org/10.3390/info15110682>
- Akanle, A. O., & Akanle, K. B. (2022). Legal analysis of the role of the judiciary in enhancing national security in Nigeria. *Journal of Law and Global Policy*, 7(1), 1–20.
- AlDaajeh, S., & Alrabaee, S. (2024). Strategic cybersecurity. *Computers & Security*, 141, 103845, DOI: 10.1016/j.cose.2024.103845
- Aldboush, H. H., & Ferdous, M. (2023). Building trust in fintech: an analysis of ethical and privacy considerations in the intersection of big data, AI, and customer trust. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 11(3), 90.
- Alhammadi, S., Alotaibi, K. O., & Hakam, D. F. (2022). Analysing islamic banking ethical performance from Maqāṣid al-Sharī‘ah perspective: evidence from Indonesia. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 12(4), 1171-1193.
- Arcot, P. P., Sayed, G., Parekh, B., Balasubramanian, J. V., & Sudheer, V. N. (2024). The interplay of ethics, culture, and society in the age of finance digital transformation. *Journal of Southwest Jiaotong University*, 59(2), 139-163.
- Arkhipov, A., Arkhipova, N., & Karminsky, A. (2021). Regulation of financial risks in emerging markets: past, present, and future. In *risk assessment and financial regulation in emerging markets' banking: trends and prospects* (pp. 33-64). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Ayemere, I. (2025). The impact of globalization on national security in Nigeria. *African Journal of Social Issues*, 8(1), 145-157.
- Babbie, E. (2020). *The practice of social research* (15th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Baldwin, D. A. (1997). The concept of security. *Review of International Studies*, 23(1), 5–26.
- Basak, B. (2024). The impact of cybersecurity threats on national security: strategies. *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Management (IJHSSM)*, 4(2), 1361-1382.
- Boone, H. N., & Boone, D.A. (2012). Analyzing likert data. *Journal of Extension*, 50(2),1–5.
- Bradley, A. R., Coyne, C. J., & Hall, A. R. (2023). *The political economy of terrorism, counterterrorism, and the war on terror*. Cambridge University Press.
- Broecker, H. (2022). Securitisation as hegemonic discourse formation. In *Securitisation as hegemonic discourse formation: an integrative model* (pp. 91-156). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Bryman, A. (2016). *Social research methods* (5th ed.). Oxford University Press.

- Bu, Q. (2024). Behind the Huawei sanction: national security, ideological prejudices or something else?. *International Cybersecurity Law Review*, 5(2), 263-300.
- Cavelty, M. D. (2024). *The politics of cyber-security*. Taylor & Francis.
- Clarke, M., Henschke, A., Sussex, M., & Legrand, T. (Eds.). (2022). *The palgrave handbook of national security* (Vol. 15). palgrave macmillan.
- Clarkson, M. B. E. (1995). A stakeholder framework for analyzing and evaluating corporate social performance. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(1), 92–117.
- Cochran, W. G. (1977). *Sampling techniques* (3rd ed.). John Wiley & Sons.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2018). *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- DiMaggio, P. J., & Powell, W. W. (1983). The iron cage revisited: institutional isomorphism and collective rationality in organizational fields. *American Sociological Review*, 48(2), 147–160.
- Donaldson, T., & Dunfee, T. W. (1994). Toward a unified conception of business ethics: Integrative social contracts theory. *Academy of Management Review*, 19(2), 252–284.
- Egejuru, K. C. (2023). *The role of a corporate governance mechanism in mitigating fraud: a case study of the Nigerian banking industry* (doctoral dissertation, university of Salford).
- Elagin, V. I., Pavlova, J. V., Levanova, E. Y., Grigorieva, I. V., & Semenov, A. A. (2021). Ensuring economic security of economic entities. in *cooperation and sustainable development* (pp. 697-702). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Etikan, I., Musa, S. A., & Alkassim, R. S. (2016). Comparison of convenience sampling and purposive sampling. *American Journal of Theoretical and Applied Statistics*, 5(1), 1–4.
- Fatoki, J. O. (2023). The influence of cyber security on financial fraud in the Nigerian banking industry. *International Journal of Science and Research Archive*, 9(2), 503-515.
- Fink, A. (2013). *How to conduct surveys: A step-by-step guide* (5th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Fischerkeller, M. P., Goldman, E. O., & Harknett, R. J. (2022). *Cyber persistence theory: redefining national security in cyberspace*. Oxford University Press.
- Freeman, R. E. (1984). *Strategic management: A stakeholder approach*. Boston: Pitman.
- Gasu, G. (2023). Reinvigorating the ethics of corporate governance in the Nigerian banking sector. *Journal of Contemporary African Legal Studies*, 1(2), 107-130
- Gelter, M. (2022). Is economic nationalism in corporate governance always a threat?. *fordham law legal studies research paper*, (4020333), 1-36.

- Gonsolin, A. I. M. (2023). *Ethics in finance and industry* (Doctoral dissertation, Politecnico di Torino).
- Goodpaster, K. E. (1991). Business ethics and stakeholder analysis. *Business Ethics Quarterly*, 1(1), 53–73.
- Gujarati, D. N., & Porter, D. C. (2009). *Basic econometrics* (5th ed.). McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
- Haynes, S. N., Richard, D. C. S., & Kubany, E. S. (1995). Content validity in psychological assessment: A functional approach to concepts and methods. *Psychological Assessment*, 7(3), 238–247.
- Heath, J. B. (2019). The new national security challenge to the economic order. *Yale Law Journal*, 129, 1020.
- Hill, K. J. (2020). *Balancing national security and the constitution: the security blanket over civil liberties* (doctoral dissertation, Johns Hopkins University).
- Jones, T. M. (1995). Instrumental stakeholder theory: a synthesis of ethics and economics. *Academy of Management Review*, 20(2), 404–437.
- Kandpal, V., Ozili, P. K., Jeyanthi, P. M., Ranjan, D., & Chandra, D. (2025). Regulation of the fintech industry. in *digital finance and metaverse in banking: decoding a virtual reality towards financial inclusion and sustainable development* (181-198). Emerald Publishing Limited.
- Khaleel, F., Janjua, P. Z., & Ahmed, M. (2022). Ethical consideration of Islamic banks in Pakistan: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 13(6), 1351–1372. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-10-2020-0327>
- Khalil, K., Manzoor, S. R., Tahir, M., Khan, N., & Jamal, K. (2021). Impact of cyber security cost on the financial performance of e-banking: mediating influence of product innovation performance. *Humanities & Social Sciences Reviews*, 9(2), 691-703.
- Kiruthika, G., Gowrishankar, M., & Kumar, P. J. (2024). Empowering sustainable development goals in the banking industry: a comprehensive analysis of ethical banking practices and economic viability. in *3rd international conference on reinventing business practices, start-ups and sustainability (ICRBSS 2023)* (426-436). Atlantis Press.
- Kitler, W. (2021). National security. *Theory and practice, Warszawa, Towarzystwo Wiedzy Obronnej*.
- La Porta, R., Lopez-de-Silanes, F., Shleifer, A., & Vishny, R. W. (1998). Law and finance. *Journal of Political Economy*, 106(6), 1113–1155.
- Likert, R. (1932). A technique for the measurement of attitudes. *Archives of Psychology*, 140, 1–55.

- Martellini, M., & Abaimov, S. (2022). Physical security, cyber security, and critical infrastructure: an introduction. in *handbook of security science* (1133-1143). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- McRae, J., Boulton, M., Baker, J. E., Burnett, R. E., Holyan, A., Stoddart, K., & McDermott, D. L.(2022). *Contextualizing Security: A Reader* (Vol.33). University of Georgia Press.
- Meyer, J. W., & Rowan, B. (1977). Institutionalized organizations: Formal structure as myth and ceremony. *American Journal of Sociology*, 83(2), 340–363.
- Mgiba, F. M., & Mxotwa, T. (2024). Communicating banking cyber-security measures, customer ethical concerns, experience, and loyalty intentions: A developing economy's perspective. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 14(3), 123–132.
- Moshi, A. (2024). The effect of perceived security risks on mobile banking adoption in the fashion retail industry: A case study of Mwanza Region, Tanzania. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 7(12), Article 28. <https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v7-i12-28>
- Naseir, M. A. B. (2021). *National cybersecurity capacity building framework for counties in a transitional phase* (Doctoral dissertation, Bournemouth University).
- North, D. C. (1990). *Institutions, institutional change and economic performance*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nunnally, J. C., & Bernstein, I. H. (1994). *Psychometric theory* (3rd ed.). McGraw-Hill.
- Ojo, A. A., & Ayo, T. E. (2023). National security, promotion of democratic tenets and the leadership role of government: a review. *International Journal of Peace and Conflict Studies*, 8(2), 59-73.
- Okodugha, N. (2021). *Central bank of Nigeria, corporate governance and the quest for sustainable banking system in Nigeria: an exploratory analysis* (Doctoral dissertation, University of East London).
- Okoye, A. C., Chikezie, A. E., & Aginam, E. V. (2025). Tensions from within: perspective on state fragility and internal security challenges in nigeria. *Integral Research*, 2(1), 99-114.
- Omarova, S. T. (2017). Ethical finance as a systemic challenge: Risk, culture, and structure. *Cornell JL & Public Policy*, 27, 797.
- Ononiwu, M. I., Onwuzulike, O. C., & Shitu, K. (2024). Comparative analysis of customer due diligence and compliance: balancing efficiency with regulatory requirements in the banking sectors of the United States and Nigeria. *World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews*, 23(3), 475-491.
- Osuma, G., Ayinde, A., Ntokozo, N., & Ehikioya, B. (2024). Evaluating the impact of systemic corruption and political risk on foreign direct investment inflows in Nigeria: an analysis of key determinants. *Discover Sustainability*, 5(1), 1-13.

- Painter-Morland, M. (2006). Redefining accountability as relational responsiveness. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 66(1), 89–98.
- Paleri, P. (2022). Rule of law and role of government: law making, enforcing and national security. In *Revisiting National Security: Prospecting Governance for Human Well-Being* (303-340). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Phillips, R. (2003). *Stakeholder theory and organizational ethics*. Berrett-Koehler Publishers.
- Pijpers, P., & Arnold, K. (2025). Rethinking cyber deterrence: adapting to the realities of the digital battlefield. *Journal of Strategic Security*, 18(1), 61-76
- Rossi, N., & Riemann, M. (Eds.). (2024). *Security Studies: An Applied Introduction*. SAGE Publications Limited.
- Rovera, C. (2022). *Ethics in banking: is it possible?*. Springer Nature.
- Ruth, N., Kituyi, M., & Kagwa, F. (2022). Ethical climate: analyzing the moderation effect on cardinal virtues and employees' cyber security ethical behavior intention in Ugandan commercial Banks. *European Journal of Technology* 6(2),49-61
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P., & Thornhill, A. (2019). *Research methods for business students* (8th ed.). Pearson Education Limited.
- Scott, W. R. (2001). *Institutions and organizations* (2nd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Sheikh, M. A., Ahmed, S. M. B., & Rana, A. A. (2022). Economic security in Pakistan: indicators, issues, impacts and way forward. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*, 4(1), 990-999.
- Sindiramutty, S. R., Jhanjhi, N. Z., Tan, C. E., Yun, K. J., Manchuri, A. R., Ashraf, H., & Hussain, M. (2024). Data security and privacy concerns in drone operations. In *Cybersecurity Issues and Challenges in the Drone Industry* (236-290). IGI Global.
- Slawotsky, J. (2024). conceptualizing national security in an era of great power rivalry: implications for international economic law. *East Asia*, (42),279–307
- Suandi, E., Herri, H., Yuliharsi, Y., & Syafrizal, S. (2023). An empirical investigation of Islamic marketing ethics and convergence marketing as key factors in the improvement of Islamic banks performance. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 14(6), 1438–1462. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-10-2021-0315>
- Sutton, L. J., & Stewart, M. G. (2002). Cost-effectiveness of security measures to prevent terrorism at Australian airports. *Journal of Air Transport Management*, 8(1), 11–18.
- Tavakol, M., & Dennick, R. (2011). Making sense of Cronbach's alpha. *International Journal of Medical Education*, 2, 53–55.
- Torku, K., & Laryea, E. (2021). Corporate governance and bank failure: Ghana's 2018 banking sector crisis. *Journal of Sustainable Finance & Investment*, 1-21.

- Treviño, L. K., Weaver, G. R., Gibson, D. G., & Toffler, B. L. (1998). Managing ethics and legal compliance: What works and what hurts. *California Management Review*, 41(2), 131–151.
- Ugbe, U. M. (2021). *Exploring the security measures to reduce cyberattacks within the nigerian banking sector: a qualitative inquiry* (Doctoral dissertation, Capella University).
- Valentine, S., & Barnett, T. (2003). Ethics code awareness, perceived ethical values, and organizational commitment. *Journal of Personal Selling & Sales Management*, 23(4), 359–367.
- Valls Martínez, M. D. C., Martín-Cervantes, P. A., & Peña Rodríguez, S. (2021). Ethical banking and poverty alleviation banking: The two sides of the same solidary coin. *Sustainability*, 13(21), 11977,
- Van Oosterhout, J., Heugens, P. P. M. A. R., & Kaptein, M. (2006). The internal morality of contracting: Advancing the contractualist endeavor in business ethics. *Academy of Management Review*, 31(3), 521–539.
- Vevere, V., & Svirina, A. (2020). Business ethics and corporate social responsibility. Retrieved from https://mail.augstskola.lv/upload/csr%20book_final_01.2020.pdf
- Viganò, L. (2020). Ethical orientation in banks: original roots in bank governance and current challenges. *Handbook on Ethics in Finance*, 1-27
- Whitman, M. E., & Mattord, H. J. (2018). *Principles of information security* (6th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2016). *Introductory econometrics: A modern approach* (6th ed.). Cengage Learning.